

Factors Influencing Substance Abuse among Adolescent in a Selected Community of Badagry Local Government Area, Lagos State

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Abstract

Substance abuse among adolescents continues to be a significant global concern, with profound implications for both youth development and national well-being. Of particular concern is the widespread prevalence of substance abuse during adolescence, a critical developmental stage. This study investigates the factors influencing substance abuse among adolescents in a selected community within the Badagry Local Government Area of Lagos State. The objectives include assessing adolescents' knowledge of substance abuse, identifying factors contributing to their engagement, and determining the most commonly abused substances. Employing a descriptive research design, the study sampled 100 adolescents using multistage and convenience sampling techniques. Data were collected through a self-designed, pre-tested questionnaire and analyzed using SPSS (version 27), with results presented in tabular form. Findings indicate that while all respondents were aware of substance abuse and its detrimental effects, key influences driving abuse include peer pressure, easy access, curiosity, poverty, pursuit of pleasure, and exposure to substance abusers in their environment. The substances most frequently abused among the adolescents are alcohol (86%), cannabis (60%), coffee (84%), cough syrup (73%), and tramadol (72%). The study concludes that despite high awareness, engagement in substance

use remains prevalent, prompting recommendations for enhanced parental supervision regarding peers, governmental restrictions on the importation of harmful substances, and stricter regulatory oversight to limit availability within communities.

Keywords: Adolescents, Substance abuse, Influencing factors, Substance use

Chapter One

Introduction

Background of the Study

Substance abuse is a major global health challenge, recognized as a significant public health issue in many countries due to its wide-ranging social, physical, and economic impacts. These consequences include poor academic performance, interpersonal conflicts, family and legal problems, addiction, and a heightened risk of HIV/AIDS, particularly among adolescents. This problem is especially prevalent among youth worldwide, posing serious social and health concerns. Substance abuse is often referred to by various terms such as drug abuse, psychoactive substance abuse, and illicit drug use. According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2021), substance abuse involves the harmful or hazardous consumption of psychoactive substances, including alcohol and illicit drugs. The American Psychiatric Association (2019) describes it as a pattern of drug use that is detrimental to the individual or

others, classified as a substance-related disorder. Similarly, WHO's Lexicon of Alcohol and Drug Terms (2021) defines substance abuse as a maladaptive use pattern, characterized by continued use despite recurring social, occupational, psychological, or physical issues caused or worsened by the substance, including use in physically hazardous situations. The Global Burden of Disease Study (2019) highlights adolescent and youth substance use as a growing public health concern due to its association with both intentional and unintentional societal problems. Globally, an estimated 271 million individuals aged 15-64 used psychoactive substances in 2019, reported by the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC). Substance use among youth is notably alarming in regions such as the United States, Latin America, and Europe, where it contributes to reduced quality of life and social challenges (OAS, 2019; EMCDA, 2019; World Drug Report, 2021). In Africa, traditional use of cannabis presents regulatory challenges, with around 28 million people consuming illegal drugs including cannabis, khat, heroin, and cocaine (Mnunguli & Kisangiri, 2018). Substance use among adolescents in Sub-Saharan Africa is estimated at around 41.6%, and 38.3% in West Africa (Olawole et al., 2018). Alcohol-related diseases are particularly burdensome in Africa due to weak legislation and enforcement (WHO Global Alcohol Status Report, 2018). Within East Africa, Tanzania leads in marijuana usage, followed by Kenya and Uganda (The Citizen Newspaper, 2019). Nigeria ranks among the countries with the highest cannabis usage, with 19.4% of the population aged 15 and above reported to have used cannabis in the previous year (UNODC World Drug Report, 2021). Drug use without medical prescription, especially among adolescents and youths, remains widespread. Commonly abused substances

include alcohol, cigarettes, codeine, marijuana, amphetamines, and tramadol (Ayandiji & Osoba, 2018; Vignan et al., 2019). Adolescence, spanning ages 10-19 according to WHO, is a critical developmental stage marked by physical, emotional, psychosocial, and behavioral changes. It is a period of exploration and vulnerability, often associated with high-risk behaviors including substance abuse. Adolescents face unique challenges, and lack of adequate support and understanding hinders their full potential (WHO).

Globally, adolescents make up approximately 1.2 billion of the world population, projected to increase to 1.23 billion by 2040. Among drug users, 24% fall within the 12-18 age group, and many begin using substances like cannabis before age 15 or between 16 and 20 years (UNODC & Ministry of Social Justice & Empowerment, 2018). Socioeconomic factors such as poverty, illiteracy, unemployment, and family instability contribute significantly to vulnerability. In Nigeria's Lagos State, where substance abuse prevalence is about 33% (NBS, 2018), escalating drug and alcohol use among adolescents is linked to juvenile delinquency, school failure, HIV/AIDS, violent crime, and social instability. Despite being preventable, substance abuse causes over 2.6 million deaths annually worldwide among young people aged 10-24 (WHO, 2021). This study was motivated by these concerns to explore adolescents' knowledge of substance abuse, identify factors influencing use, and propose interventions within a selected community in Badagry Local Government Area of Lagos State, which is densely populated with significant drug use challenges.

Statement of the Problem

Despite global attention and educational efforts, many adolescents lack sufficient awareness of the psychosocial risks of

substance abuse. Parents and community members often fail to provide adequate moral guidance. Although agencies like the National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA) and NAFDAC implement anti-drug strategies, recent data indicate that 40% of underage groups are already engaged in drug use (NDLEA, 2021). This trend threatens societal security through increased antisocial behaviors, including violence, crime, school dropout, and sexual offenses. The economic burden from enforcement, lost productivity, and incarceration is substantial for Nigeria's fragile economy. Identifying contributing factors is critical to inform prevention and education programs and address this growing menace.

Objective of the Study

The primary aim of this study is to assess factors influencing substance abuse among adolescents in a selected community within Badagry Local Government Area, Lagos State. Specific objectives include:

- Assessing adolescents' knowledge of substance abuse.
- Identifying factors influencing substance abuse among respondents.
- Determining the common substances abused by adolescents.

Research Questions

- What is the level of knowledge about substance abuse among the respondents?
- What factors contribute to substance abuse among the adolescents?
- Which substances are commonly abused by the respondents?

Hypothesis

HO: There is no significant relationship between respondents' religious beliefs and their knowledge about substance abuse.

The results of this study will provide valuable insights for healthcare providers,

community organizations, and policymakers to design targeted awareness campaigns focused on the dangers of substance abuse among adolescents. For nurses and clinicians, findings will enhance assessment tools and support the development of individualized intervention programs for substance abuse treatment, promoting quicker recovery and reducing hospital stays. Socially, the study will help guide community sensitization efforts to curb substance abuse and its linked antisocial behaviors, thereby improving security and peace. Economically, a more focused young population with reduced drug use can enhance productivity and national development. The study's findings will also assist government agencies in formulating effective policies and strategies to combat substance abuse.

Scope of the Study

This research focuses on factors influencing substance abuse among adolescents aged 10-19 in a selected community within Badagry Local Government Area, Lagos State, regardless of their religious, cultural, educational, or socioeconomic background.

Operational Definitions

- **Factors:** Specific elements influencing substance abuse, including psychosocial, knowledge-based, and sociocultural factors such as peer pressure, family structure, and personality traits.
- **Psycho-social factors:** Influences like peer pressure, social media, occupation, personality traits (e.g., shyness, impulsiveness), and family environment (e.g., monogamy, polygamy, divorce).
- **Knowledge factors:** Awareness and understanding of substance abuse and its consequences.
- **Patients:** Adolescents aged 10-19 residing in the selected community who have engaged in substance abuse.

- **Substance abuse:** The inability to control the use of substances such as cannabis, alcohol, tramadol, cocaine, diazepam, cigarettes, and meth that affect mental processes and create physical or psychological dependence.

Chapter Two

Literature Review

Introduction

This chapter presents a review of existing literature related to factors contributing to substance abuse among adolescents in the Badagry Local Government community, Lagos State. It also explores potential strategies for addressing the issue and identifies gaps that this study aims to fill.

Conceptual Review

Substance abuse is conceptually understood as the reckless use of substances despite awareness of their potential dangers, often leading to addiction. This addiction is marked by intense cravings, tolerance, and dependence, which are physiological adaptations in the central nervous system (CNS) following repeated substance use. Over time, tolerance increases, requiring higher doses to achieve the desired effects (NIDA, 2020). Drug: A drug is any substance (aside from food that provides nutrition) that, when inhaled, ingested, injected, absorbed, or smoked, causes temporary physiological and often psychological changes in the body. Drug Aware (2018) defines a drug as any substance excluding food and water that alters body functions physically and/or psychologically. Drugs may be legal (e.g., alcohol, tobacco, caffeine) or illegal (e.g., cannabis, cocaine, heroin), with psychoactive drugs affecting the central nervous system to influence mood, cognition, and behavior. They are typically classified as depressants, stimulants, hallucinogens, or other types. Dowshen

(2018) describes drugs as chemical substances that alter bodily functions, while NIDA (2020) highlights their impact on brain communication systems by disrupting neuronal signaling. Substance Abuse: Drug abuse is variously defined but broadly refers to the compulsive, excessive, and harmful use of habit-forming substances leading to addiction or dependence, causing serious physical and psychological harm or death (Business Dictionary, 2018). Jerome et al. (2018) emphasize its maladaptive and addictive nature where drugs are used without medical justification, with emotional and physical compulsions driving continued use.

Knowledge of Substance Abuse Among Respondents

Knowledge plays a crucial role in fostering healthy behaviors (Leah, 2018). Njoroge (2018) found that university students' lack of awareness about substance use risks correlates with increased consumption; factors such as availability, media, and technological influences contribute to this. Abibe et al. (2022) reported that the majority of secondary school students in Nsukka were aware (80.5%) and knowledgeable (83.2%) about the health risks of substance misuse. Information sources included family, teachers, medical outreaches, and media campaigns warning about the dangers of substance use.

Commonly Abused Substances Among Respondents

Despite stringent global laws, adolescents commonly use psychoactive substances worldwide. WHO (2020) estimated 275 million substance users globally in 2020, most aged 15-26, representing 5.5% of the population. Regional variations include heroin and opium dominance in Afghanistan; high sedative and tranquilizer use among children in Albania (WHO,

2022). The opioid epidemic is critical in the US, Canada, and Bangladesh, while methamphetamine is prevalent in China, South Korea, and Japan (WHO, 2020). In Africa, cannabis is the most frequently used psychoactive substance among students, with approximately 34 million users, and substance use is rising in Sub-Saharan secondary schools (WHO, 2019). Alcohol is the leading consumed substance in Southern Africa and a major risk factor for cancer and psychiatric disorders. Large multinational alcohol companies have significantly increased alcohol consumption, especially in Ethiopia. Substance abuse is often viewed as a moral failing in Nigeria, leading to low treatment-seeking behavior by families (Musyoka et al., 2020; Adebisi & Owoaje, 2018). Notably, kolanut, alcohol, and tobacco are the most common substances among Nigerian secondary students, with alcohol consumption three times the global average at 15% (Olalekan, 2019). Without intervention, there is a projected rise in drug addiction among Nigerian adolescents by 2030. In Lagos State, alcohol use among senior secondary school students is high, with 77.2% reporting lifetime consumption (Adibe et al., 2022). Similarly, a Tanzanian study found marijuana, cigarettes, and alcohol as the most commonly used psychoactive substances among secondary students (Ochieng, 2022).

Factors Influencing Substance Use Among Respondents

Understanding motives behind adolescent substance abuse is vital for shaping prevention programs. Various studies identify peer pressure, family context, and local availability as key factors influencing youth substance use (Ochieng, 2022). Joel (2018) notes that adolescents also use substances to enhance mood, gain social acceptance, or cope with negative emotions. Akindipe & Aina (2021) cite Akanni et al.'s

study revealing significant associations between having friends or family members who use substances and adolescent use of tobacco, alcohol, cannabis, and caffeine. Factors such as gender (male), age, dissatisfaction with parental or teacher relationships, and polygamous family background also correlate with increased substance use. Rukundo et al. (2019) emphasize peer influence as the dominant driver of adolescent substance abuse in Uganda, alongside family and community factors. Neighborhood social contacts also facilitate substance use transmission among students. Students reported using drugs to boost confidence during social activities. Demographic and socioeconomic variables affect substance abuse risks. High religiosity, better parental education, and living with parents reduce abuse likelihood, whereas higher family socioeconomic status may increase it, possibly due to greater resource availability and social pressures (Akindipe & Aina, 2021). Conversely, economic hardship can drive abuse as a survival mechanism, highlighting complex socio-economic dynamics.

Adewumi (cited in Akindipe & Aina, 2021) found that despite good knowledge of substance abuse consequences and a strong desire to quit, addiction undermines efforts due to its compulsive nature. Duru et al. (2018) reported that males, individuals from broken homes, and those with lower education levels are more likely to abuse psychoactive substances, while medical students demonstrated lower usage rates. Other motives identified in Sokoto include family conflict, peer pressure, curiosity, stress adaptation, and influences from media and antisocial role models. Media adverts promoting alcohol and tobacco, often employing celebrities, strongly sway adolescents. Peer pressure and emulation of drug-abusing role models further promote substance use.

Effects of Drugs and Substance Abuse

Adolescence is a key period for establishing lifelong habits that impact personal development and society. Substance abuse during this time can lead to negative health outcomes and developmental challenges (National Academies of Sciences, 2019). Tobacco use begun in adolescence increases risks of emphysema, various cancers, and heart disease later in life. Diraditsile & Rasesigo (2018) found that substance abuse significantly affects mental health, contributing to depression, stress, personality and mood disorders, psychosis, and suicidal tendencies, with depression being the most prevalent. Mood disorders often co-occur, resulting in irritability and hopelessness.

Measures to Combat Drug and Substance Abuse

Health education often views knowledge as a catalyst for behavioral change (Kelly &

Barker, 2018). However, knowledge alone is insufficient; behavior change requires relevant, applicable knowledge combined with life skills. Arlinghaus & Johnston (2018) stress that knowledge must raise awareness and resonate personally to influence behavior. Effective intervention for adolescents must go beyond simple awareness of psychoactive substances' harms to include empowerment and skill-building to resist peer pressure and substance offers. Research supports that low knowledge increases risk, while higher knowledge correlates with reduced positive attitudes towards substance use and lower future use likelihood (Idowu et al., 2018; Panuele et al., 2022; Ifeoma et al., 2020). Educating Nigerians on the health risks associated with psychoactive substances is thus essential.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework for the study adapted from theory of reasoned action by Fishbein and Ajzen, (1975).

Theoretical Review

Theory of Reasoned Action

This theory posits that behavior is driven by deliberate intention formed through attitudes and subjective norms. Attitude refers to an individual’s positive or negative evaluation of performing a behavior, shaped by beliefs about outcomes and their value. Subjective norms involve perceived social pressure from significant others to engage or not engage in the behavior. Normative social influence compels individuals to conform to behaviors expected by important social

groups, such as friends and family, to gain acceptance, even if they personally disapprove. The theory emphasizes that strong attitudes and norms enhance behavioral intentions. Key tenets include:

- Behavioral outcomes and public opinion influence individual actions.
- Behavior is shaped by intention, which depends on attitudes and subjective norms.
- Attitudes stem from personal evaluation of expected behavior outcomes.

Perceived Behavioral Control complements this by explaining how behavior is contingent on one’s perceived ability and volitional control to perform or avoid an action.

Figure 2: Theory of reasoned action by Fishbein and Ajzen, (1975). As cited by Aina et al., 2021

Application of the Theory of Reasoned Action To This Study

The Theory of Reasoned Action is particularly relevant to this study because its core concept—*intention*—serves as the closest predictor of behavior. Intention reflects the degree to which an individual

plans and commits effort toward engaging in a specific behavior. This intention arises from two belief-based components: attitudes and subjective norms, both of which are influenced by background factors.

Disposition: This refers to the individual’s genetic makeup and personality traits, such as self-esteem and emotional stability, which affect self-efficacy. These characteristics shape a person’s capacity to accept or reject

behaviors, especially under the influence of important social figures like friends, peers, or family members.

Demographic Factors: Elements such as age, education level, occupation, family structure, and religion play a crucial role in shaping an individual's ability to make definitive decisions about engaging in certain behaviors.

Information: The extent of a person's exposure to knowledge about the consequences and perceived benefits of substance use significantly influences their attitude toward substance abuse.

Attitude toward the Behavior: This involves the perceived personal benefits that may encourage engagement in substance abuse, such as gaining social acceptance from peers, experiencing increased confidence, or escaping personal problems.

Subjective Norms: These are the social pressures and influences from significant others that affect an individual's intention to either accept or reject particular behaviors. Examples include peer pressure, past experiences, and social media influences. Interventions like youth social clubs focused on substance abuse awareness and policies regulating substance use could reinforce positive behaviors, shift public perception, and strengthen individuals' favorable attitudes while discouraging negative intentions, promoting responsible conduct regarding substance use.

Behavioral Intention: This is the decision an individual makes after weighing the influences of significant social factors and logically assessing relevant personal considerations. This intention directly precedes and shapes the actual behavior,

which in this context is the engagement in substance abuse.

Empirical Review

Knowledge of Substance Among Respondents

A study by Ogochukwu et al. (2022) examining knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding substance use among Nigerian secondary school students found that a large majority were both aware (80.5%) and knowledgeable (83.2%) about the health risks associated with substance use. Specifically, 78.3% of students recognized that substance misuse could cause liver damage, while 76.0% acknowledged its link to cardiovascular disease. However, overall knowledge about the relationship between substance use and violence was moderate, at 52.5%. Similarly, research by Aina and Joseph (2021) investigating factors influencing substance abuse among patients admitted to two federal neuropsychiatric hospitals in southwestern Nigeria revealed that most respondents possessed good knowledge of substance abuse and its consequences—60.6% in Yaba and 58.2% in Aro.

Factors Influencing Substance Use Among Respondents

Reported factors contributing to substance use among secondary school students include curiosity (51.7%), lack of awareness of substance misuse complications (42.2%), peer pressure (40.8%), low self-confidence (40.1%), and easy access to drugs (35.6%) (Ogochukwu et al., 2022). Aina and Joseph (2021) also identified peer pressure, social media influence, occupation, family environment, and personality traits as key contributors, with 69.4% and 71.1% of respondents acknowledging peer pressure and personality traits, respectively, as influential factors. Afoke et al. (2021) studied socio-demographic influences on

drug abuse among undergraduates in Ebonyi State's tertiary institutions. They found that students whose peers used drugs showed higher levels of drug abuse (63.0%) compared to those whose peers were non-users (63.6% high level but differing statistically with $p = 0.09 > 0.05$). The study upheld the hypothesis that peer drug use significantly correlates with an individual's drug abuse level. Similarly, parental drug use also appears influential: 62.6% of students with drug-using parents demonstrated high levels of drug abuse, compared to 67.0% among those whose parents were non-users. Overall, 70.4% of respondents reported parental drug use in some form, underscoring the impact of peer and parental influences on adolescent substance use.

Commonly Abused Substances Among Respondents

Ogochukwu et al. (2020) reported that among students, tramadol (56.5%), alcohol (77.7%), and marijuana (73.8%) were the most commonly abused substances.

Aina and Joseph (2021) found that alcohol abuse was more prevalent in Aro (81.8%) than in Yaba (53%), whereas cannabis abuse was slightly higher in Yaba (71.2%) compared to Aro (69.1%). Cannabis was the most prevalent substance overall, followed by alcohol and codeine; substances such as pentazocine (8.3%) and diazepam (9.1%) had the lowest prevalence among respondents.

Chapter Three

Methodology

Introduction

This chapter outlines the research methodology employed in the study. It details the research design, study location, target population, sampling techniques, as well as the methods used for data collection and analysis.

Research Design

A descriptive cross-sectional survey design was utilized for this research. This design was chosen because the study was conducted within a limited timeframe and required collecting data from a sample representing the population to investigate factors influencing substance abuse among adolescents in a selected community within Badagry Local Government Area, Lagos State. The descriptive approach facilitates gathering factual information about the current state of the phenomenon without any manipulation of variables.

Research Setting

The study took place in a chosen community within Badagry Local Government Area in Lagos State. Badagry is a coastal town and LGA situated on the northern bank of Porto Novo Creek, a waterway linking Lagos, Nigeria's largest city and economic hub, to Porto-Novo, the capital of Benin. This route also connects Lagos, Ilaro, and Porto-Novo, and shares a border with the Republic of Benin. As the second largest town in Lagos, Badagry had an estimated population of 351,900 in 2022. The LGA comprises 11 wards, each reflecting a rich diversity of cultures, beliefs, ethics, and languages. These wards are Ajara, Ajido, Apa, Awhanjigoh, Ibereko, Ilogbo-Araromi, Iworo Gbanko, Iya-Afin, Keta-East, and Posukoh.

Target Population

The study focused on adolescents who are currently involved in or have previously engaged in substance abuse. A total of 100 respondents were selected and participated in the study.

Sampling

A sample size of 100 was derived from Cochran's formula;

$$N = \frac{Z^2PQ}{e^2}$$

$$E^2 \dots$$

where;

N-sample size

$$z = 1.962$$

p=level of precision (0.063), (Ogundele et al.,2021).

$$q = 1 - P$$

E = 0.05 (constant)

$$N = \frac{Z^2 PQ}{E^2}$$

$$N = 1.96^2 * 1.96 * 0.063 * (1 - 0.063) / 0.05^2 * 0.05$$

$$= 0.2267734896 / 0.0025$$

$$= 90.709.$$

Therefore, 10% of 90.709 = 9.070.

$$N - 90.709 + 9.070 = 99.779, \text{ approximately } 100.$$

N-100.

Sampling Techniques

A multistage sampling method was employed to select the study participants. Initially, wards within the local government area were randomly selected using simple random sampling. Subsequently, communities within these wards were chosen. The final selection of respondents was done through convenience sampling.

Inclusion Criteria: Adolescents who have engaged in substance abuse, aged between 10 and 19 years, who were deemed fit to participate, and who consented to take part in the study.

Exclusion Criteria: Individuals who never abused substances, those younger than 10 years, and those older than 19 years were excluded.

Instrument of Data Collection

Data was collected using a self-designed questionnaire, which was pretested and validated. The reliability coefficient calculated using Cronbach's Alpha was 0.8. The questionnaire comprised four sections:

- a) Respondents' socio-demographic information
- b) Knowledge about substance abuse
- c) Factors influencing substance abuse
- d) Commonly abused substances

The questionnaire was administered to respondents with the support of two trained research assistants.

Validity of Instrument

To ensure face and content validity, the questionnaire was developed in alignment with the study objectives and reviewed by experts for approval. All recommended modifications were incorporated before its use in data collection.

Reliability of Instrument

A pilot study was conducted to assess the instrument's internal consistency and stability. Ten questionnaires (10% of the intended sample size) were distributed to adolescents with similar characteristics in other communities. The Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient obtained was 0.78.

Method of Data Collection

Questionnaires were administered with assistance from trained research assistants after obtaining consent from community authorities and participants. Participants were given adequate time to complete the questionnaire and informed that involvement was voluntary, with the option to withdraw at any time. Confidentiality of responses was assured. Participants were also notified that no immediate personal benefits would result, but the research aimed to enhance knowledge about substance abuse. Literate respondents completed the questionnaire themselves, while non-literate respondents had the questions read aloud and responses recorded by the assistants.

Method of Data Analysis

Data were analyzed quantitatively using descriptive statistics such as frequency tables, percentages, and cross-tabulations to present findings. Inferential analysis was conducted using the Chi-square test to evaluate hypotheses at a significance level of 0.05. All statistical procedures were performed using SPSS version 27 software.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the Lagos State College of Nursing Research Committee.

Participants’ willingness to participate was sought, and only those who provided informed consent were included. The consent form was explained as needed. The study upheld principles of autonomy and confidentiality. Information was communicated in accordance with the respondents' educational levels and preferred languages. The purpose of the study was to generate knowledge to aid the development of strategies aimed at reducing psychoactive substance abuse.

**Chapter Four
Results**

Introduction

This chapter presents the findings derived from the data gathered from the study respondents. It includes the statistical analysis of the respondents’ demographic characteristics as well as responses to the research questions. The collected data were organized through classification, editing, coding, and tabulation. Analysis was performed according to the study objectives using statistical methods, including charts and frequency distribution tables.

Table 1: Respondent’s Socio-Demographics characteristics (n=100).

AGE	Frequency	Percentage
10-14	11	11.0%
15-17	30	30.0%
18-19	59	59.0%
Total	100	100%
GENDER		
Male	64	64.0%
Female	36	36.0%
Total	100	100%

RELIGION		
Christianity	40	40.0%
Islam	40	40.0%
Others	20	20.0%
Total	100	100%
ETHNICITY		
Yoruba	70	70.0%
Igbo	20	20.0%
Hausa	10	10.0%
Total	100	100%
Family TYPE		
Monogamous	42	42.0%
Extended	31	31.0%
Polygamous	27	27.0%
Total	100	100%
EDUCATIONAL LEVEL		
Monogamous	15	15.0%
Extended	70	70.0%
Polygamous	15	15.0%
Total	100	100%

Table 1 above illustrates that the majority of respondents were aged 18 to 19 years, with a mean age of 2.4800. The gender distribution shows that 64% of participants were male, while 36% were female. The Yoruba ethnic group constituted 70% of the sample. Christianity and Islam were equally represented as the dominant religions, each accounting for 40% of the respondents. tertiary education levels each accounted for 15% of the respondents.

It is important to note that the prevalence of the Yoruba ethnicity and these religious affiliations was not intentionally selected but rather reflects the demographic characteristics of the research community. Furthermore, the table indicates that most respondents came from monogamous families (42%), followed by those from extended families (31%) and polygamous families (27%). Regarding educational status, around 70% of participants were enrolled in secondary school, while both primary and

Answering Research Questions

Table 2: Respondent`s Knowledge level on Substance abuse

STATEMENTS	SA	A	U	D	SD	TOTAL
I have heard of term substance abuse	55(55%)	45(45%)				100%
I am aware that substance abuse is harmful	40(40%)	60(60%)				100%
Use of tobacco is a form of substance abuse	30(30%)	40(40%)	30(30%)			100%
Indiscriminate use of drug constitutes substance abuse	15(15%)	85(85%)				100%
Use of un-prescribed drug is a form of substance abuse	15(15%)	80(8%)	5(5%)			100%
TOTAL	155(155%)	310(310%)	35(35%)			500%

Table 2 above indicates that over 99% of respondents were familiar with the term "substance abuse." All respondents (100%) were aware of the harmful effects associated with substance abuse. Additionally, 70% recognized tobacco use as a form of substance abuse, while 30% remained uncertain. The table further shows that all respondents agreed that the indiscriminate

use of drugs constitutes substance abuse. Lastly, more than 90% acknowledged that using unprescribed drugs is a form of substance abuse, with 5% expressing uncertainty on this point. In conclusion, majority of the respondents have vast knowledge of substance abuse and effects which constitute about 97%.

Table3: Factors influencing substance abuse among adolescent in the selected community

STATEMENTS	SA	A	U	D	SD	TOTAL
Peer pressure is a motive behind substance abuse	80(80%)	20(20%)				100(100%)
Poor parentage is a motive behind substance abuse	10(10%)	40(40%)		21(21%)	29(29%)	100(100%)
Easy access to drug is a factor behind substance abuse	30(30%)	50(50%)	10(10%)		10(10%)	100(100%)
Curiosity is a motive behind Substance abuse	40(40%)	40(40%)		10(10%)	10(10%)	100(100%)
Poverty is a motive behind substance abuse	10(10%)	10(10%)	20(20%)	30(30%)	30(30%)	100(100%)
Low self-confidence is a motive behind substance abuse	10(10%)	30(30%)	20(20%)	20(20%)	20(20%)	100(100%)
Joy seeking is a motive behind substance abuse	20(20%)	40(40%)	30(30%)	10(10%)		100(100%)
Lack of access to consultation centers is a motive behind substance abuse	20(20%)	20(20%)		40(40%)	20(20%)	100(100%)
Presence of an addicted person is a motive behind substance abuse	35(35%)	25(25%)	20(20%)	10(10%)	10(10%)	100(100%)
TOTAL	255(255%)	275(275%)	100(100%)	141(141%)	129(129%)	900(900%)

Table 3 above reveals that over 99% of respondents (80% strongly agreeing and 20% agreeing) identified peer pressure as a key factor influencing their involvement in substance abuse. Half of the respondents (10% strongly agreeing and 40% agreeing) cited poor parenting as a motive, while the other 50% (21% disagreeing and 29% strongly disagreeing) rejected this as a factor. More than 79% affirmed that easy access to substances contributes to substance use, with 10% strongly disagreeing and another 10% undecided. The table also shows that curiosity prompted substance abuse for most respondents, with about 80% strongly agreeing and 20% disagreeing.

Poverty was regarded as a motivating factor by 60% (strongly agreeing), while 20% agreed and 10% were undecided. Concerning low self-esteem, 40% agreed it influenced their substance use, 40% disagreed, and 20% remained undecided. Approximately 60% reported using substances for joy-seeking purposes, 30% disagreed, and 10% were undecided. Regarding access to consultation centers, 40% agreed it was a reason for substance use, whereas 60% disagreed. Lastly, about 60% agreed that being around addicted individuals influenced their substance use, while 20% strongly disagreed and another 20% were undecided.

Table 4: What are the commonly abused substances among Adolescents?

SUBSTANCE	YES	NO
Alcohol	86(86%)	14(14%)
Marijuana	60(60%)	40(40%)
Heroin	29(29%)	71(71%)
Ice	27(27%)	73(73%)
Cigarette	40(40%)	60(60%)
Inhalant	39(39%)	61(61%)
Coffee	84(84%)	16(16%)
Codeine	50(50%)	50(50%)
Tramadol	72(72%)	28(28%)
Cough syrup	73(73%)	27(27%)
Kola nut	40(40%)	60(60%)
TOTAL	600(600%)	500(500%)

Table 4 above illustrates the prevalence of various substances abused by respondents. The majority, 86 respondents (86%), reported having abused alcohol, while 14 (14%) had not. Cannabis abuse was reported by 60 respondents (60%), with 40 (40%) indicating no use. The data show that alcohol had the highest prevalence, followed by coffee at 84% (84 respondents), cough syrup at 73% (73 respondents), and tramadol at 72% (72 respondents). In contrast, substances such as ice (27%), heroin (29%),

and inhalants (39%) exhibited the lowest rates of abuse among the respondents.

Hypothesis Testing

Null Hypothesis (H0): There is no significant relationship between the respondents’ religious beliefs and their knowledge of substance abuse.

Table 5: The relationship between knowledge level and abuse of a substance

Religion	Christianity	Islam	Others	Total	X ²
p-value					
Knowledge of substance Good	40		40	13	93
30.108^a .0000					
abuse					
Poor	0	0	7	7	
Total	40	40	20	100	

Table 5 above presents the chi-square test results for knowledge, yielding $X^2=30.108$ with a p-value of 0.0000. Given that the p-value is less than the 0.05 significance level, it can be concluded that there is no significant association between

the respondents’ religious beliefs and their level of knowledge about substance abuse.

Chapter Five

Summary, Conclusion, And Recommendations

Introduction

This chapter provides a discussion of the study's findings, summarizes key results, explores their implications for nursing, presents recommendations, acknowledges study limitations, and offers suggestions for future research.

Discussion of Findings

As shown in Table 1 above, the age distribution of respondents indicated that 11% were aged 10–14 years, 30% were 15–17 years, and 59% were between 18 and 19 years, demonstrating that the majority of substance abusers are young adults. The study found a higher proportion of males (64%) compared to females (36%), aligning with findings by Akindipe and Aina (2021). Table 2 revealed that 55% strongly agreed and 45% agreed that they had heard of the term substance abuse. Additionally, 60% and 40% acknowledged that substance abuse is harmful. This indicates a good level of knowledge about substance abuse and its negative effects among respondents, consistent with findings by Aina et al. (2021) and Adewumi (2019). Despite this awareness, addiction often undermines their ability to quit. Notably, respondents in neuropsychiatric hospitals may have gained this knowledge through ongoing treatment. Early psycho-education on substance abuse consequences could help reduce its prevalence. Table 3 above identified peer pressure, easy access, curiosity, joy seeking, and proximity to addicted persons as major influences on substance abuse. Peer pressure was cited by 85% of respondents, supporting research by Duru et al. (2019) and Akindipe et al. (2021) emphasizing its strong role. Easy accessibility was acknowledged by 80%, reflecting findings by Chibuike et al. (2020).

Curiosity was also a significant factor, reported by 80%, consistent with Murtala's (2020) observations concerning risk-taking behaviors among youth, as supported by Balarabe et al. (2018, 2019). Interestingly, 80% of respondents disagreed that poverty drives substance abuse, while 60% reported substance use for mood enhancement and social confidence, echoing studies by Akindipe (2021), Alhyas, and Adeoti (2018). Access to consultation centers as a factor was contested, with 60% disagreeing and 40% agreeing. Presence of addicted individuals in respondents' environment contributed for 60%, while 40% disagreed. Table 4 above showed high prevalence of alcohol (86%), coffee (84%), marijuana (60%), tramadol (72%), and cough syrup (73%) abuse—findings that concur with Adibe et al. (2022), who reported widespread alcohol and other drug use among secondary school students in Nigeria. Substances such as methamphetamine, inhalants, heroin, and kola nut were less prevalent. Similar patterns were noted by the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC, 2018). Table 5's chi-square test indicated no significant association between respondents' religious beliefs and their knowledge of substance abuse, consistent with Aina's (2021) research showing no correlation between gender, education level, religion, and substance abuse knowledge.

Implications For The Nursing Profession

The study confirms that substance abuse among adolescents in Badagry Local Government Area poses serious mental health concerns and threatens future societal leadership. Rising abuse correlates with increased rehabilitation admissions and crime rates, negatively impacting national development. Nurses and healthcare providers have a critical role in educating adolescents and their families about the dangers of substance abuse through routine

interactions, including antenatal and postnatal care.

Given nurses' frontline position in managing patients with substance abuse disorders, they should prioritize health education on prevention, risk factors, and treatment options to reduce addiction and support recovery.

Limitations of the Study

Challenges encountered included:

- Reluctance of some respondents to disclose information about hard drug use due to legal concerns.
- Limited openness from participants concerned about social stigma affecting honesty about substance abuse.
- Limited time for data collection and report preparation, given the wide study area.
- Financial constraints impacting study scope and resources.

Summary

Substance abuse involves loss of voluntary control over substance use, leading to health and social dysfunction. Psychoactive substance misuse poses significant challenges, especially for adolescents transitioning to adulthood. The study identified peer pressure, curiosity, joy seeking, easy access, low self-confidence, and nearby addicted individuals as key influencing factors. Most respondents were young adults (18–19 years), a critical demographic for workforce and economic stability. Approximately 93% exhibited good knowledge of substance abuse consequences, though addiction often undermines behavioral change. Peer pressure and curiosity were the strongest influences, with alcohol and coffee as the most commonly abused substances. Statistical analysis confirmed no relationship between religious belief and knowledge of substance abuse, highlighting the need for

early educational interventions to reduce addiction risk.

Conclusion

The prevalence of substance abuse among adolescents in the study area is high, with alcohol, marijuana, cigarettes, and tramadol being the most commonly abused substances.

Peer influence, personality traits, and joy seeking significantly impact substance abuse, particularly among those aged 18 to 19. Targeted interventions for this age group are essential to mitigate adverse effects on national productivity. Religious beliefs were not associated with knowledge levels of substance abuse, indicating that reinforcing moral values within families can be key to reducing use. Accessibility, curiosity, peer pressure, and personality remain significant contributors. Addressing these specific factors through tailored interventions and prevention programs in schools, correctional facilities, and community settings is critical. Adjusting school curricula to alleviate stress may also reduce psychoactive drug use among students.

Recommendations

In light of the findings, the following are recommended:

- i.** Parents should actively monitor and support their children, fostering open communication and awareness of their social circles, while providing moral, spiritual, psychological, and financial support.
- ii.** Strengthening positive parent-child relationships and educating youth on drug dangers is vital.
- iii.** Social institutions such as families, schools, and religious centers should reinforce moral values and ethics to counter peer pressure.
- iv.** The government should regulate and restrict sales of harmful substances like alcohol and cigarettes, especially limiting

youth access based on age.
v. Development of affordable and accessible recreational facilities such as sports and tourist centers should be prioritized to engage youth constructively.
vi. Regulatory bodies must closely monitor substance distribution channels and enforce strict, impartial laws against illegal use.
vii. Early psycho-education focusing on primary and secondary school students should be intensified to prevent addiction onset.

Suggestions for Further Study

Future research should explore factors influencing abuse of other drugs and substances among youth in diverse settings. Replicating this study across other local governments and communities in Lagos State would provide broader insights.

References

Adebiyi, A. O. & Owoaje, E. T.; Tobacco uses amongst out of school adolescents in a Local Government Area in Nigeria. *Subst Abuse Treat Prev Policy* 2018, 5, 24. doi:10.1186/1747-597x-5-24

Adewumi, B.O (2017). Psychosocial Factors Influencing Substance abuse among Undergraduate. *www.preprints.org*. Doi:20944/preprints2017//.0151.

Adibe MO, Anene-Okeke CG, Igboeli NU, Anosike C. Knowledge, attitude, and practice of substance use in Nigeria among secondary school students. *CHRISMED J Health Res* 2022;9:23-30. afro. who, int/health-topics/substance-abuse

Akindipe A.P., Aina J.O. (2021), Factors Influencing Substance Abuse among Patients Admitted to the two Federal Neuro-Psychiatric Hospitals in the South-West of Nigeria. *African Journal of Health, Nursing and Midwifery* 4(2), 38-66. DOI: 10.52589/AJHNMIEQS9BNG.

Alhylas, L., OZaibi, N.A., ELarabi, H., El-kashef, A. (2015). Adolescents' perception

of substance uses and factors Influencing it's use. *JRSM open* 6(2) 205427041456716 www.iwww.imedpub.com/medpub.com

APA (2019). A Study of factors contributing to drugs abuse in selected public secondary Schools in Miriga Meru Imenti North, Unpublished thesis MA University of Nairobi, Kenya.

Arlinghaus, K. R. & Johnston, C. A. (2018). Advocating for Behavior Change With education. *American journal of lifestyle medicine*, 12 (2), 113-116. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1559827617745479>

Ayandiji, A. & Osoba, P. (2018). Social and Psychological Effects of Drug Abuse among Rural Youths in Ogun State. *International Journal of Health and Pharmaceutical Research* ISSN 2045-4673 Vol.3 No.4 2017 www.iiardpub.Org

Diraditsile, K., & Rasesigo, K. (2018). Substance Abuse and Mental Health Effects among the Youth in Botswana: Implications for Social Research. *Journal of Education, Society and Behavioural* 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.9734/JESBS/2018/38304>" *Science*, 24(2).

Dowshen, S. (2018). What you need to know about Drugs. *Kids health from Neumors*. Edwards, G. & A. Arif, eds. Introduction to: drug problems in the sociocultural context: a basis for Policies and Programme Planning. *World Health Organization Offset Publication No. 73*. 18.

Duru, C.B, Oluoha U.R, Okafor, C.C, Diwe K.C, Iwu, A.C, Aguocha C.M, Ohale 1 & Nwaigbo (2017). Socio-Demographic Determinants of Psychoactive Substance Use among Students of Tertiary Institutions in Imo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Addiction Research & Therapy* 8 (3), 2155-6105.

EMCDA. (2019). Drug and Alcohol Use among Young People: Annual report on the state of the drug problem in the European Union and Norway. www.emcdda.europe.eu GBD2019DemographicsCollaborators

Global age-sex-specific fertility, mortality, healthy life expectancy (HALE), and population estimates in 204 countries and territories, 1950-2019: a comprehensive demographic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2019" 9/fulltext#:~:text=13.GBD,Disease%20Study%202019, <http://www.businessdictionary.com/definition/drug-abuse.html>
<https://drugaware.com.au/getting-the-facts/faqs-ask-a-question/what-are-drugs/#/what-is-a-drug>
<https://worldmapper.org/maps/population-year-2018/>
[https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/P11S0140-6736\(20\)30925-](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/P11S0140-6736(20)30925-)
Idowu, A., Aremu, A.O, Olumide A, & Ogunlaja, A.O. (2018). Substance abuse among students in selected secondary schools of an urban community of Oyo-state, South West Nigeria: implication for policy action. *African Health Sciences* 18(3): 776-785. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.4314/ahs.v18i3.36>
Ifeoma, O. J., Grace, N., Chimezie, N., Bashir, I. W., Ngozi, O. G., Uzochukwu, A. F., & Onyemaechi, N. P. (2020). Effect of Drug Abuse and Health Risks Among Undergraduates of Federal Universities in Nigeria. *Global Journal of Health Science*, 12, 107
Jerome Nyame, Magaji, I, Yakubu, Susan Teru & Agnes Titus (2018), Economic Implications of Drug Abuse among the Youths. *Journal of Economic and Sustainable development*.
Joel, M. (2018). Factors Influencing Drug and substance Abuse among Public Secondary School Students in Kiambu County, Kenya. *International Journal of Psychology*. www.iprjb.org
Johnson, O.E, Akpanekpo, E. I, Okonna, E.M, Adeboye S.E, & Udoh, A.J. (2018). The Prevalence and Factors affecting Psychoactive Substance Use among Undergraduate Students in University of

Uyo, Nigeria. *Journal of Community Medicine and Primary Health Care*. 29 (2) 11-22
Kelly, M. P. Barker, M. (2018) Why is changing health related behavior so difficult? *Public Health* 2016; 136: 109-116. [PMC free article] [PubMed]
Leah, M. (2018). Substance use education resources. Retrieved from <https://www.Projectknow.com/research/substance-use-education-resources/>
Mnunguli, J. P. & Kisangiri, M. (2018). Evidence Based Practices for Drug Abuse Information Management and Awareness Approaches. *Journal of Information Systems Engineering & Management*, 3(4), 31. <https://doi.org/10.20897/Jisem/3942>
Musyoka, C. M., Mwayo, A., Donovan, D., & Mathai, M. (2020). Alcohol and Substance Use among First-year Students at the University of Nairobi, Kenya: Prevalence and Patterns. *PLoS One*, 28, 15(8), e0238170. Doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0238170.
National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), (2018): *Drug Use in Nigeria*.
National Institute of Health. (2020). *Monitoring the Future Study: Trends in Prevalence of Various Drugs*. Retrieved from *Monitoring the Future Study: Trends in Prevalence of Various Drugs National Institute on Drug Abuse (NIDA)* [46] National Instit
Njoroge M.W (2018), Knowledge, Attitude and Practices on Substance Use Disorders by University Students. *Journal of Alcoholism & Drug Dependence*,5(6) DOI: 10.4172/2329-
OAS. (2019) Annual Report of the Inter-American Drug Abuse Control Commission (CICAD), to the General Assembly of the Organization of American States at its fifteenth regular session: [CICAD/doc.2523/20](https://www.cicad.oas.org/doc/2523/20).
Olalekan, R.M., Funmilayo, A.A., Iteimowei, M., Okoyen, E., B.O. (2019).

Public Health Impact of Substance Use on Adolescent: A Snapshot of Yenagoa in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. *Am Journal of Biomed Science & Research*, 4(3).

Olawole-Isaac, A. Ogundipe, O, Amoo, E O. & Adeloje, D. (2018), Substance use among adolescents in subSaharan Africa: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *South African Journal of Child Health*, 12 (7), 79-84.

R. M., Funmilayo, A. A. Iteimowei, M., Okoyen, E., Oyinlola, B. O. (2019). Public Health Impact of Substance Use on Adolescent: A Snapshot of Yenagoa in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. *Am Journal of Biomed Science & Research*, 4 (3)

Rukundu. A.Kibanja.M &Steffens. (2019). Factors influencing psychoactive substance use among adolescents in public secondary schools in Uganda October 2017 the *International Journal of Alcohol and Drug Research* 6(1):69

DOI:10.7895/ijadr.v6i1.237

The Citizen Newspaper. (2019), Tanzania leads East Africa in marijuana consumption: Report Retrieved from: <https://magazetini3.rssing.com/chan65451559/article108933.html?zx=81> 4, June, 21st 2022.

United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC). Global Overview of Drug Demand and Supply. *World Drug Report*. United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime; 2018.

UNODC, *World Drug Report* 2018.

Vigna-Taglianti F, Alesina M, Damjanović L., Mehanović E, Akanidomo I, Pwajok J, Prichard G. van der Kreeft P, Virk HK: Unplugged Nigeria Coordination Group. (2019). Knowledge, attitudes and behaviours on tobacco, alcohol and other drugs among Nigerian secondary school students: Differences by geopolitical zones. *Drug Alcohol Review*, 38 (6): 712-724.

WHO Global status report on alcohol and health. Geneva: WHO, 2018.

WHO. (2020). Global School-based Student Health Survey: Mauritania fact sheet. Geneva. World Health Organization.

World Drug Report, (2018). United Nations publication retrieved from <https://www.unodc.org>

[www.imedpub.com/Journal of Addictive Behaviors and Therapy](http://www.imedpub.com/Journal_of_Addictive_Behaviors_and_Therapy)

World Drug Report. (2021). *Drug Market Trends: Cannabis and Opioids* (United Nations Publication, Sales No. E.21.X1.8).

World Health Organization. (2021). Alcohol. Harmful use of alcohol. Retrieved from <http://www.who.int/healthtopics/alcohol#tab tab 1>.

World Health Organization. (2021). Substance Abuse: Overview. Retrieved from <https://www.who.int/health-topics/substance-abuse>.